

Reaction of Punshi and Phouoibi to leaf blast and gall midge in Manipur, India, 1979.^a

Subdivision	Punshi		Phouoibi		IR24 (check)		Phouren (check)	
	SS (%)	Blast score	SS (%)	Blast score	SS (%)	Blast score	SS (%)	Blast score
Imphal West I	22.04	2-3	26.78	1-4	43.58	1-3	9.60	0-1
Imphal West II	12.71	5-6	14.19	3-4	10.80	3-5	3.92	0-3
Imphal East	32.44	3-4	26.05	1-4	29.32	2-4	6.19	1-2
Thoubal	23.85	4-5	38.33	3-6	23.26	2-6	5.07	0-1
Bishenpur	14.98	3-6	16.89	3-5	9.36	2-4	6.46	0-2

^aSS = silvershoot. Blast score is by the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

midge (see table). Further field observations later confirmed their susceptibilities.

In addition, Punshi is occasionally infected, from nursery to late tillering stage, with leaf scald caused by *Rhyn-*

chosporium oryzae. Standard Evaluation System for Rice (1980) scores range from 3 to 5.

Bacterial blight resistance in donor varieties having other desirable traits

S. S. Malik and R. S. Paroda, Haryana Agricultural University, Regional Research Station, Uchani, Kanal, India

To isolate a multiple donor variety for bacterial blight (BB), stem rot (SR), brown planthopper (BPH), stem borer

(SB), and blast (BI) for use in the breeding program, 30 desirable varieties were tested for reactions to BB. The experiment was conducted under artificial epiphytotic conditions at Haryana Agricultural University, May-October 1981.

Two 5-m-long rows of each variety were artificially inoculated at maximum tillering. Inoculation was done by cutting 5 cm of the upper leaf portion with

a sickle dipped in a single-isolate inoculum. The inoculum was prepared by soaking small pieces of naturally infected leaves in water for 20 minutes.

Disease reactions were compared 15 days after inoculation. The standard IRTP evaluation (scale 1-9) was used. Disease intensity had reached 9 in susceptible varieties.

BJ 1 and DV 85 showed resistance and appeared to be a suitable donor for BB. Dasal, FR 43B, Mahsuri, IET 4141, Chuigak-45, TKM6, LZN, UPRB 30 and 31, and CB 1 were moderately resistant. Three varieties had intermediate resistance. All others tested were susceptible to BB (see table). These studies showed varieties TKM6 and BJ 1 are resistant to BB. They also have desirable grain character and plant type.

Reaction of various donor varieties to bacterial blight at Karnal, India.^a

Variety	Donor for	Other desirable trait(s)	Reaction to BB ^b
CH 1039	High altitude	-	5
Patnai 23	Salt resistance	Resistant (R) to B1, BS, SB	9
Dasal	Salt resistance	-	3
Getu	Salt resistance	Tolerant (T) of salinity	5
SR 26 B	Salt resistance	-	7
Basmati-370	Salt tolerance, SR resistance	R to BI	7
Jhona 349	Alkali tolerance	-	9
FR 43B	Flood resistance	-	3
FR 13A	Flood resistance	R to SR	7
Mahsuri	Lowland	-	3
Jagannath	Lowland	-	7
Lalnakanda 41	Upland, drought tolerance	-	9
MTU 17	Upland, drought tolerance	-	9
Kataribhog	RTV	-	9
Latisail	RTV	-	9
ARC 6650	BLS resistance	R to BPH, WBPH, RTV	7
IET4141	BB resistance	-	3
Chuigak-45	BB resistance	-	3
DV 85	BB resistance	-	1
TKM6	BB and SB resistance	R to BI, RTV, GLH, BPH, SSB, SR	3
BJ 1	BB resistance	R to BI, BLS, SB	1
LZN	BB resistance	R to BI	3
UPRB 30	BB resistance	-	3
UPRB 31	BB resistance	R to BI	3
IR8	BI resistance	-	7
Carreon	BI resistance	R to BLS	7
Tadukan	BI resistance	R to BLS	5
CB 1	SB resistance	-	3
Siam 29	GM resistance	R to BI, BLS	9
CR94-721-3	GM	-	7

^aBI = blast, BB = bacterial blight, BLS = bacterial leaf streak, BPH = brown planthopper, BS = brown spot, GLH = green leafhopper, GM = gall midge, SB = stem borer, SR = stem rot, SSB = striped stem borer, RTV = rice tungro virus, - = not tested. ^bOn a scale of 1-9: 1 = resistant, 9 = susceptible.

Seedling age and incidence of rice dwarf

Bharat P. Upadhyay, assistant plant pathologist, National Rice Improvement Programme, Parwanipur, Nepal; H. E. Kauffman, director, International Soybean Program, Illinois, USA; and D. B. Lapis, senior research fellow, Plant Pathology Department, IRRI

Rice dwarf (RD), the only rice virus disease presently reported in Nepal, is transmitted by the green leafhopper *Nephotettix nigropictus*. RD also occurs in Japan, Korea, and Taiwan.

A greenhouse experiment, conducted at Khumaltar Agriculture Station, Kathmandu, Nepal, in July 1981, examined the effect of rice seedling age on